

Success Criteria

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

An exercise to establish and formulate your consortium's intentions and goals, and how to evaluate whether they have been successful.

Benefits

This exercise enhances the understanding of diverse interests and ideas. It helps to align and phrase intentions and targets in the proposal development. Your multi-actor consortium will be required to get on the same page in terms of actions and activities and how the consortium will evaluate their success.

Practical recommendations

Introduction (5 min)

During the introduction, the facilitator explains the four key concepts:

- Intention: the idea that you plan to carry out
- Target: the target outcome of the idea
- Successful if: the indicator(s) that prove that the criteria are met
- Failure if: the indicator(s) that prove that the criteria are not met

Round 1 – Setting the intentions (10 min)

Ask participants to write down their intentions/ideas related to the proposal on sticky notes. What types of ideas or intentions do they have on the call? Depending on the size of your group, you can ask participants to either do this individually or in small (2-3 pers.) groups. The facilitator groups and summarises ideas.

Round 2 – Thinking about targets (10 min)

Ask participants to think about a target outcome for each of the intentions identified in Round 1. What kind of outcome would support the intention? The facilitator groups and cleans up notes before going into round 3.

Round 3 – Success and failure (10 min)

Participants are asked to think for each target outcome what would be criteria for success and failure. These criteria should be measurable.

Round 4 – Reflection (15 min)

Have a reflection in group about the sticky notes on each of the lines. You can plan to pick this exercise up again later, or build further on it at a later point in time.

Credit: This workshop format is sourced from FunRetrospectives (<https://www.funretrospectives.com/>)

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Work with a diversity of professional backgrounds

Communicate transparently about agendas, expectations and results

Be comfortable with co-ownership and responsibility of tasks, results and outcomes

Balance needs of both yourself and the consortium as a whole

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Success Criteria by FunRetrospectives](#)

**right click to open*